

AI-Fabricated Case Law and the Ethical Standards of the Brazilian Bar Association

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Abstract: This article critically analyzes the practice of using generative artificial intelligence to draft court filings containing nonexistent case law, a phenomenon arising from the combination of AI hallucinations and the absence of specialized human review. Drawing on concrete cases documented in both Brazilian and U.S. courts, the study demonstrates that the submission of fictitious precedents does not constitute a mere technical error, but rather legally relevant conduct capable of violating ethical and professional duties imposed on attorneys. The correlation between this practice and the provisions of the Brazilian Bar Association Statute (Estatuto da Advocacia) and the Code of Ethics and Discipline of the OAB (Brazilian Bar Association) is systematically examined, with emphasis on the duties of truthfulness, good faith, loyalty, professional diligence, and liability for negligence. The article also engages with national and international frameworks on the responsible use of artificial intelligence, highlighting the centrality of the human oversight principle. Finally, practical guidelines aimed at mitigating the risk of AI hallucinations and preserving the credibility of professional practice are presented, reaffirming that the use of AI in the legal profession does not diminish, but rather reinforces, the ethical and legal responsibility of the attorney.

Keywords: Generative artificial intelligence. AI hallucination. Attorney professional ethics. Fabricated case law. Disciplinary liability.

INTRODUCTION

This article aims to analyze how the practice of filing court pleadings containing AI-fabricated case law violates the Brazilian Bar Association Statute (Estatuto da Advocacia) and the OAB Code of Ethics and Discipline, identifying which specific provisions are directly breached.

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From a methodological standpoint, this study adopts a legal-dogmatic approach, employing document analysis and case studies based on episodes involving the use of generative artificial intelligence in legal filings containing nonexistent case law references. The empirical scope focuses on occurrences documented between 2024 and 2025, identified through primary sources (judicial decisions, appellate rulings, and procedural records referenced in the text); however, when access to the primary record was not publicly available on a stable basis, secondary sources were used, while maintaining the criterion of selecting episodes with clear procedural or disciplinary consequences. The case selection prioritizes situations in which there is express mention of AI use and in which the procedural or disciplinary consequence demonstrates the legal relevance of the conduct.

More than three years after ChatGPT was launched to the public in November 2022, the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) by the legal profession has become a well-established fact. Data collected by the OAB São Paulo Chapter in partnership with Jusbrasil indicate that 62% of attorneys at law firms and private companies regularly use artificial intelligence, while this figure reaches 63% among legal professionals in the public sector and 55.1% among legal professionals overall (JUSBRASIL, 2025).

The potential contribution of this technology to legal work is well recognized, given its high efficiency when properly used, as demonstrated: “consultants using AI were significantly more productive (they completed 12.2% more tasks on average, and completed tasks 25.1% more quickly)” (DELL’ACQUA *et al.*, 2023). However, excessive reliance on AI-generated output can lead to a phenomenon known as AI complacency, as defined: Wiener (1981) defined complacency as “a psychological state characterized by a low index of suspicion” (WIENER, 1981, apud PRINZEL III *et al.*, 2001, p. 7).

Complacency occurs, given its very nature as previously explained, only when the user fails to implement the critical step of specialized human review in their AI workflow. The importance of this step is evidenced by its inclusion in Resolution No. 49/2023 of the OAB Acre Chapter, whose Article 5 lists human oversight among its guiding principles, defining it as “maintaining specialized human control and supervision over the use of AI, with legal professionals evaluating and validating the actions and results generated by the technology to

ensure accuracy, ethical compliance, and legal conformity” (ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL – SECCIONAL ACRE, 2024).

In addition to being established in the first regulation governing artificial intelligence in Brazilian legal practice (MIGALHAS, 2024) and in Recommendation 01/2024 of the CFOAB (CONSELHO FEDERAL DA ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL, 2024), the duty of review is also enshrined as a principle in various international and sector-specific frameworks, including: the OECD Council Recommendations on AI; the UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence; the Council of Europe Framework Convention on Artificial Intelligence, Human Rights, Democracy and the Rule of Law; EU Regulation 2024/1689 (AI Act); the African Union Continental Strategy for Artificial Intelligence; and UN Resolution A-RES-78-311.

AI complacency becomes an even more apparent and serious problem when one considers the existence of another phenomenon, more intrinsic to the operation of the technology itself: AI hallucination.

As defined in the specialized literature, “an AI hallucination occurs when the model makes an error in its probabilistic calculation, resulting in the generation of a fabricated or incorrect response” (VASCONCELOS, 2025, p. 56).

The operation of an AI system such as an LLM is based on probabilistic calculations, as Murphy (2022, p. xxviii) explains: “using the same unifying lens of probabilistic modeling and Bayesian decision theory”. Thus, when this calculation goes wrong, false information emerges, known as hallucination; this is the primary cause of the phenomenon. Furthermore, OpenAI recently published a groundbreaking study disclosing the discovery of an even more fundamental origin for the problem, revealing that the feedback methodology used in training AI systems causes future errors in the presentation of untruthful information in the output of the systems (KALAI et al., 2025).

It is the combination of AI hallucination with the absence of output review (complacency) on the part of the legal user that constitutes the subject of this study: court filings containing fabricated case law.

1. CASES OF COURT FILINGS WITH FABRICATED CASE LAW

Before analyzing Brazilian cases of court filings containing fabricated case law, it is appropriate to examine several occurrences documented in U.S. courts.

The examination of foreign cases serves to demonstrate that the phenomenon is not limited to the Brazilian legal profession.

In May 2025, the Utah Court of Appeals, in *Garner v. Kadince*, sanctioned one of the attorneys of record for nonexistent citations generated by AI. The opinion describes the use of fictitious precedents – one of them a purported *Royer v. Nelson* – and imposed compensatory and remedial measures on the attorney, reaffirming the duty of human verification before filing (ESTADOS UNIDOS. UTAH. COURT OF APPEALS, 2025).

In September 2025, the California Court of Appeal found that 21 of 23 citations in the appellate brief were fabricated by AI tools, imposing a \$10,000 sanction on the attorney and referring the case to the State Bar to which the attorney was admitted. The Court noted that the failure lay not in the use of AI itself, but in the omission of the duty to verify the authenticity and relevance of the cited material. As the first case on which the California Court of Appeal ruled on this matter, the decision became a national reference (ESTADOS UNIDOS. CALIFÓRNIA. COURT OF APPEAL, 2025).

Still in the U.S. context, it is worth noting that trial courts have also confronted this problem. Judge David Hardy of Nevada, faced with 14 nonexistent citations in memoranda signed by two attorneys at Cozen O'Connor, replaced conventional fines with remedial measures, including mandatory letters to the deans of the law schools from which they graduated reporting the incident, as well as ordering lectures on ethics and AI and other procedural consequences (MERKEN, 2025).

Within the Brazilian jurisdiction, without claiming to be exhaustive, the following representative cases of the same phenomenon are presented.

At the Santa Catarina Court of Appeals (Tribunal de Justiça de Santa Catarina), an attorney filed a *habeas corpus* petition containing nonexistent case law citations. The presiding appellate judge noted that the act constituted bad faith and disrespect to the court, emphasizing that the submitted legal precedents “were fabricated to mislead the adjudicator” and formally admonished the

attorney for the conduct, although the petition was accepted for review by the Court (MIGALHAS, 2025c).

In Londrina, in proceedings before the 2nd Federal Court, an attorney repeatedly filed motions containing false information, including nonexistent statutory provisions, reference to a purported “Procedural Law of Time” (a nonexistent statute), and citations to case numbers and rulings that could not be found in any court. Federal Judge Igor de Lazari Barbosa deemed the conduct irresponsible, as the attorney had used the technology “without proper verification of the generated content” and found bad-faith litigation and conduct detrimental to the dignity of the judiciary, imposing two fines of 10 minimum wages on the attorney. The judge further ordered that the matter be referred to the OAB for disciplinary investigation (MIGALHAS, 2025a).

Not even practice before the Brazilian Supreme Court (Supremo Tribunal Federal) is immune to the phenomenon of fabricated judicial decisions. In May 2025, Justice Cristiano Zanin denied a constitutional complaint whose petition had been drafted with the aid of AI, identifying citations to nonexistent rulings and incorrect interpretation of legal statements. Sanctions for bad faith were imposed, and a referral was ordered to the Federal Council of the OAB and the relevant state chapter for disciplinary action. This stands as a paradigmatic reference at the apex of the Brazilian judicial system, with an explicit reprimand for unsupervised use of AI in court filings (MIGALHAS, 2025d).

Finally, the most high-profile case stands out, likely due to the sheer volume of fabricated rulings. The Paraná Court of Appeals (Tribunal de Justiça do Paraná) documented an appeal whose text, according to the reporting judge, had been produced by AI and contained forty-three nonexistent rulings, including decisions attributed to judges who had not served during the periods indicated. The court rejected the appeal, admonished the attorney of record, and referred the case to the OAB for investigation, underscoring the professional duty to critically verify any content generated by automated tools before signing the filing (MIGALHAS, 2025b)

These cases demonstrate that the phenomenon under analysis recurs in both Brazilian and U.S. jurisdictions.

2. ANALYSIS OF THE CORRELATION BETWEEN THE CONDUCT AND THE PROVISIONS VIOLATED

2.1. The OAB Code of Ethics and Discipline

The OAB Code of Ethics and Discipline establishes, among its fundamental principles, a core set of non-waivable duties that directly relate to situations of automation without review. Upon analysis, one identifies three central provisions that are violated by the use of artificial intelligence without proper specialized human oversight, resulting in the fabrication of case law.

First, the sole paragraph of Article 2 establishes duties, including: “II – to act with courage, independence, honesty, propriety, truthfulness, loyalty, dignity, and good faith.” (ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL, 2015). The practice of fully automating legal research and drafting without human control and oversight compromises truthfulness and good faith, because the attorney relinquishes the technical act of verifying facts and precedents, exposing the client and the court to potentially false information.

Next, Article 6 categorically provides: “It is forbidden for the attorney to present facts in court or in administrative proceedings by deliberately distorting the truth and acting in bad faith” (ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL, 2015). Even when the falsehood originates from an artificial intelligence tool, by signing the filing the attorney assumes intellectual and legal authorship of its content, such that the absence of minimum review converts the machine’s error into a misrepresentation attributable to the attorney, particularly when simple and accessible means of verification exist.

Even where direct intent as required by the provision is not established in every case, the conduct may reveal at least a conscious assumption of risk or qualified negligence, sufficient to ground ethical-disciplinary liability in light of the duty of professional care.

Finally, Article 9 of the same statute provides: “The attorney must inform the client, clearly and unequivocally, of any risks inherent to the client’s claim and of the consequences that may arise from the proceeding. [...]” (ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL, 2015). It is legally defensible to argue that the attorney also bears the duty to inform the client of the specific risks associated with the use of generative AI without verification, such as the risk of hallucination,

nonexistent citations, and procedural sanctions, as such risks may directly affect the strategy and outcome of the case.

2.2. The Brazilian Bar Association Statute (Estatuto da Advocacia)

The Estatuto da Advocacia (Brazilian Bar Association Statute), in its chapter “On the Ethics of the Attorney”, establishes a public standard of conduct and a framework of objective liability for negligent behavior.

Article 31 provides: “The attorney shall conduct themselves in a manner that renders them worthy of respect and contributes to the prestige of the profession and the practice of law.” (ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL, 2024). Signing an unreviewed filing containing fictitious citations undermines the profession and negatively impacts public trust in the legal profession, offending institutional prestige.

Article 32 of the Statute provides that “The attorney is liable for acts committed in the exercise of the profession with intent or negligence.” (ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL, 2024). The failure to review the output of the AI before filing the pleading constitutes, at minimum, fault through recklessness or negligence, attracting liability for procedural and disciplinary harm.

The same statute continues in Article 33: “The attorney is obligated to rigorously comply with the duties set forth in the Code of Ethics and Discipline.” (ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL, 2024). Failure to observe the duties of truthfulness, loyalty, and good faith prescribed by the Code of Ethics constitutes a simultaneous violation of the Statute.

Finally, Article 34 must also be analyzed, which establishes as particularly relevant infractions:

“IX – to harm, through gross negligence, an interest entrusted to one’s representation; [...] XIV – to distort the content of a legal provision, doctrinal citation, or judicial ruling [...]; [...] XXIV – to commit repeated errors evidencing professional ineptitude; XXV – to maintain conduct incompatible with the practice of law” (ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL, 2024).

Filing a pleading containing nonexistent or distorted precedents due to lack of review falls within the scope of gross negligence with potential harm to the client; moreover, the distortion of judicial rulings, even if negligent, materializes in fact when the text improperly reproduces decisions; the repetition of filings with

the same defect suggests professional ineptitude; and the totality of the conduct may be characterized as incompatible with the practice of law.

In borderline cases, where the attorney merely activates the AI and does not effectively participate in the drafting, it is defensible to invoke subsection V, “signing any document intended for judicial proceedings or extrajudicial purposes that one did not prepare, or in which one did not collaborate” (ORDEM DOS ADVOGADOS DO BRASIL, 2024), given the degree of technical detachment from the content.

3. TECHNIQUES FOR MITIGATING AI HALLUCINATION

The specialized literature presents practices aimed at reducing the occurrence of AI model hallucination and mitigating its effects when it does occur. These techniques may be employed cumulatively (VASCONCELOS, 2025).

3.1. Use of Reasoning Models

Leading AI systems offer models with reasoning capabilities, such as GPT-5.2 Thinking, Anthropic Claude Thinking, and Google Gemini Thinking. This capability means that, before executing the request, the AI processes the details of the query through a prior deliberative step, consistent with OpenAI’s statement (2024a): “[...] trains them to reason explicitly about these specifications before answering”. Just as prior planning tends to improve the results of any human activity, the same holds true for AI models, which is why the hallucination rate is significantly reduced in reasoning models. Official benchmarks that measure the hallucination rate of each model are also available (OPENAI, 2024b).

3.2. Enabling Model Honesty

Another relevant practice is enabling model honesty. According to the aforementioned OpenAI study, one of the research findings was that AI models have difficulty acknowledging that they lack certain knowledge or that they cannot perform a given task. Including directives in the prompt instructing the AI to disclose when it cannot accomplish something or when the requested information does not exist, rather than providing a forced response, contributes to controlling the occurrence of hallucinations.

3.3. Constraining the Model's Scope of Action

Additionally, constraining the model's scope of action and using reference texts are two complementary techniques. Generative AI systems possess a broad repertoire and diverse capabilities, encompassing knowledge across a wide range of fields. When processing a legal request, the model must contend with its entire body of non-legal knowledge, which can cause errors in probabilistic calculations and generate hallucinations. It is therefore advisable to delimit the model's scope through restrictive rules inserted in the prompt. A título de exemplo, ao realizar pesquisa de artigo científico com a IA, pode-se inserir no prompt such as "search exclusively in scientific sources." Such restrictions do not disqualify the excluded sources but rather direct the model toward the desired type of result. Similarly, when a reference text is available for analysis, it is recommended to instruct the AI with commands such as "conduct the analysis exclusively based on the attached file. You are prohibited from searching the internet."

3.4. Requesting Supplementary Questions

It is also useful to add a directive to the prompt instructing the AI, before executing the main request, to formulate supplementary questions aimed at gathering information the user may not have provided. In this way, the model has greater context for task execution, potentially incorporating data that the user did not consider relevant. To do so, one need only add the instruction: "Before executing the task, ask 5 questions to gather supplementary information you deem necessary." The number of questions can be adjusted according to the complexity of the request.

3.5. Enabling the Search Function

Additionally, it is recommended to enable the internet search function available in major AI systems when updated information is needed or when one wishes to ensure that the returned results contain verifiable sources.

3.6. Conducting Specialized Human Review

Finally, although it is not a practice exclusive to avoiding hallucination, specialized human review remains an indispensable step. Upon completion of

any task processed with AI assistance, the generated content must be reviewed in its entirety so that any remaining hallucinations can be identified and corrected before filing.

FINAL REMARKS

This article has demonstrated that the phenomenon of AI hallucination is real and occurs in legal practice in both Brazil and other nations. The nature of the occurrence was analyzed, the corresponding violations of the Estatuto da Advocacia (Brazilian Bar Association Statute) and the Code of Ethics and Discipline were identified, and techniques aimed at expanding control over AI-generated outputs and preventing the insertion of fictitious case law in court filings were presented.

As demonstrated by the cases examined, the existing regulatory framework in the Brazilian legal system is sufficient to hold an attorney ethically accountable for signing a court filing containing fabricated precedents. The duties of truthfulness, good faith, professional diligence, and procedural loyalty, established in both the Estatuto da Advocacia and the OAB Code of Ethics and Discipline, apply regardless of whether the falsehood originates from human error or algorithmic failure. An AI tool does not possess legal personhood, is not subject to the disciplinary regime, and cannot bear ethical-professional liability; consequently, attribution falls entirely on the signing professional. Verifying the existence of the precedent, confirming its authenticity in official repositories, and examining the correspondence between the headnote and the full opinion are minimum diligence measures required of the attorney before filing any court document.

In this context, Recommendation No. 001/2024 of the Federal Council of the OAB deserves particular attention, as it reinforces that the final decision on legal matters must be human, and that the attorney is responsible for validating information, verifying its accuracy, and ensuring that decisions and strategies are grounded in careful human analysis. This Recommendation, combined with the international frameworks analyzed throughout this article, consolidates the principle of human oversight as a central guideline for the responsible use of artificial intelligence in legal practice.

The legal profession is expected to exercise rigorous review over work produced with the aid of artificial intelligence and preserve the credibility expected of professional practice. The adoption of hallucination mitigation techniques, such as those presented in this study, does not constitute a mere recommendation of best practices, but rather a direct consequence of the ethical and legal duties governing the practice of law. The advancement of regulation in this area, at both the legislative and institutional levels, tends to lend greater normative weight to these duties, reinforcing that the incorporation of AI into legal work does not reduce, but rather expands, the attorney's responsibility to the client, the judiciary, and society.

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